

tentacle02_individualv04 (english)

Variable Name	Question Text	Saved Value						
start	Hidden from user	Timestamp of form open						
end	Hidden from user	Timestamp of form save						
today	Hidden from user	Today's date						
deviceid	Hidden from user	Device ID (IMEI, Wi-Fi MAC, Android ID)						
authuser	Hidden from user	Username on device						
g1	Hidden from user							
qdate_sys	Today's date	User selected date						
qdate_sys_isok	Is the date correct?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
qdate_e1	What is today's date?	User selected date						
note_qd1	You have previously indicated that the system date is incorrect. The date you entered instead is the same as the system date. Please go back and either enter the correct date or indicate that the system date is correct.	User entered text						
qdate_e2	Please confirm today's date.	User selected date						
note_qd2	The dates you entered do not match. Please go back and enter and/or confirm the correct date.	User entered text						
qdate	Hidden from user							
loc	Recruitment location	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Chikwawa</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Blantyre</td> </tr> </table>	1	Chikwawa	2	Blantyre		
1	Chikwawa							
2	Blantyre							
g2	Hidden from user							
hid_scan	1.Scan the Household ID	User captured barcode						
gn_hid	Hidden from user							
hid_scan_fail	1a.Why were you unable to scan the Household ID	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Technical error (wrong value scanned)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Dirty (unscannable) barcode sticker.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>No barcode sticker; hand written ID</td> </tr> </table>	1	Technical error (wrong value scanned)	2	Dirty (unscannable) barcode sticker.	3	No barcode sticker; hand written ID
1	Technical error (wrong value scanned)							
2	Dirty (unscannable) barcode sticker.							
3	No barcode sticker; hand written ID							

		9 Other								
hid_e1	1b.Enter the Household ID.	User entered text								
hid	Hidden from user									
hid_valid	Hidden from user									
note_hid2	\$(0)is NOT a valid Household ID. Please go back and scan or enter a valid Household ID.	User entered text								
g3	Hidden from user									
pid_scan	2.Scan the Participant ID.	User captured barcode								
gn_pid	Hidden from user									
pid_scan_fail	2a.Why were you unable to scan the Participant ID	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Technical error (wrong value scanned)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Dirty (unscannable) barcode sticker.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>No barcode sticker; hand written ID</td> </tr> <tr> <td>9</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Technical error (wrong value scanned)	2	Dirty (unscannable) barcode sticker.	3	No barcode sticker; hand written ID	9	Other
1	Technical error (wrong value scanned)									
2	Dirty (unscannable) barcode sticker.									
3	No barcode sticker; hand written ID									
9	Other									
pid_e1	2b.Enter the Participant ID.	User entered text								
pid	Hidden from user									
pid_valid	Hidden from user									
pid_enrolled	Hidden from user									
pid_name	Hidden from user									
agemp	Hidden from user									
luvisit	Hidden from user									
hiv	Hidden from user									
pidhid	Hidden from user									
pidhid2	Hidden from user									
note_pid2	\$(1)is NOT a valid Participant ID. Please go back and scan or enter a valid Participant ID.	User entered text								
hidpid	\$(1)does NOT belong to this Household. Please go back and scan or enter a valid Participant ID or Household ID.	User entered text								
newpart	3.Is this a new participant in the house?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									

confirm_name	4. Is the participant's name \${2}?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
visit	5. Which visit is this?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Visit 1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Visit 2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Visit 3</td> </tr> </table>	1	Visit 1	2	Visit 2	3	Visit 3		
1	Visit 1									
2	Visit 2									
3	Visit 3									
generated_note_name_48	The participant is not scheduled for this visit	User entered text								
g4	Hidden from user									
name	Hidden from user									
ptfirstnames	5a. First name (s)	User entered text								
ptsurname	5b. Family name	User entered text								
g5	Hidden from user									
dob	6. Date of birth	User selected date								
_dob_dtype	6b. Is the date of birth complete?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Complete (Day-Month-Year)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Partially complete (Month-Year)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Partially complete (Year Only)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>88</td> <td>Unknown</td> </tr> </table>	1	Complete (Day-Month-Year)	2	Partially complete (Month-Year)	3	Partially complete (Year Only)	88	Unknown
1	Complete (Day-Month-Year)									
2	Partially complete (Month-Year)									
3	Partially complete (Year Only)									
88	Unknown									
generated_note_name_58	You indicated that date of birth is partially complete (Month-Year) but you have not entered 15 for day. Please go back and check the hint under the question.	User entered text								
generated_note_name_59	You indicated that date of birth is partially complete (Year Only) but you have not entered 15 for day and Jun for month. Please go back and check the hint under the question.	User entered text								
generated_note_name_60	The date of birth you have entered is out of range.	User entered text								
g6	Hidden from user									
ageg	Age	User entered integer								
ageunit	Age Unit	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Years</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Months</td> </tr> </table>	1	Years	2	Months				
1	Years									
2	Months									
ageyrs	Hidden from user									
agem	Hidden from user									
assent	Has informed assent been given by the participant if the child is between the ages of 8-18?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes						
1	Yes									

		0	No
consent	Has informed consent for the participant (if <18 years old) been given to take part in the study?	1	Yes
		0	No
indvsex	8.Participant Gender	1	Male
		0	Female
hhrel	9.Relationship to household head	1	Parent
		2	Grandparent
		3	Child
		4	Sibling
		5	Spouse
		6	Self
		99	Other relative
		7	Non relative
hhrelo	Please specify relationship to household head	User entered text	
slept	Has the participant slept in the house for at least 7 of the last 14 nights prior to enrollment?	1	Yes
		0	No
el1	Hidden from user		
stool	Has a stool sample been provided?	1	Yes
		0	No
stoolid	Stool sample ID	User entered text	
nostoolwhy	Why has a stool sample not been collected?	1	Participant declined
		2	Currently not sleeping in household
		3	Unable to give sample
		4	Sample to be collected another day

howlong	How long have you lived at this address?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>less than one month</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>1-6months</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>6months to 1 yr</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>1-5 years</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>>5years</td></tr> </table>	1	less than one month	2	1-6months	3	6months to 1 yr	4	1-5 years	5	>5years						
1	less than one month																	
2	1-6months																	
3	6months to 1 yr																	
4	1-5 years																	
5	>5years																	
anothaddr	Do you have another permanent address apart from this household?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No												
1	Yes																	
0	No																	
howfar	How far away is this?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Within 100m</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>100-500m</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>500-1000m</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>1000-5000m</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>>5000m</td></tr> </table>	1	Within 100m	2	100-500m	3	500-1000m	4	1000-5000m	5	>5000m						
1	Within 100m																	
2	100-500m																	
3	500-1000m																	
4	1000-5000m																	
5	>5000m																	
howlong2	How much time over the past year is spent at this other address	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>less than one month a year</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>1-6months a year</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>6months to 1 yr</td></tr> </table>	1	less than one month a year	2	1-6months a year	3	6months to 1 yr										
1	less than one month a year																	
2	1-6months a year																	
3	6months to 1 yr																	
gotosch	Do you go to school at the moment?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No												
1	Yes																	
0	No																	
schname	Name the school	User entered text																
grpOccupation	Hidden from user																	
occupation	What is your occupation?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Agriculture</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Domestic service</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Unskilled manual</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Skilled manual</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Sales and services</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Student</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Unemployed</td></tr> <tr><td>99</td><td>Other</td></tr> </table>	1	Agriculture	2	Domestic service	3	Unskilled manual	4	Skilled manual	5	Sales and services	6	Student	7	Unemployed	99	Other
1	Agriculture																	
2	Domestic service																	
3	Unskilled manual																	
4	Skilled manual																	
5	Sales and services																	
6	Student																	
7	Unemployed																	
99	Other																	

occupationother	Please specify occupation	User entered text														
edulevel	What was the last level of education that you completed?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="1235 159 1278 259">1</td> <td data-bbox="1278 159 1493 259">No formal schooling</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1235 259 1278 398">2</td> <td data-bbox="1278 259 1493 398">Primary incomplete or complete</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1235 398 1278 456">3</td> <td data-bbox="1278 398 1493 456">Primary complete</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1235 456 1278 557">4</td> <td data-bbox="1278 456 1493 557">Secondary incomplete</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1235 557 1278 658">5</td> <td data-bbox="1278 557 1493 658">Secondary complete</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1235 658 1278 714">6</td> <td data-bbox="1278 658 1493 714">Tertiary or higher</td> </tr> </table>	1	No formal schooling	2	Primary incomplete or complete	3	Primary complete	4	Secondary incomplete	5	Secondary complete	6	Tertiary or higher		
1	No formal schooling															
2	Primary incomplete or complete															
3	Primary complete															
4	Secondary incomplete															
5	Secondary complete															
6	Tertiary or higher															
workinhcare	Do you work in a school, college or healthcare?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="1235 768 1278 831">1</td> <td data-bbox="1278 768 1493 831">Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1235 831 1278 887">0</td> <td data-bbox="1278 831 1493 887">No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No										
1	Yes															
0	No															
placetype	What type of place is this?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="1235 947 1278 1010">1</td> <td data-bbox="1278 947 1493 1010">Hospital (gov)</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1235 1010 1278 1066">2</td> <td data-bbox="1278 1010 1493 1066">Health centre (gov)</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1235 1066 1278 1122">3</td> <td data-bbox="1278 1066 1493 1122">Pharmacy (gov)</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1235 1122 1278 1178">4</td> <td data-bbox="1278 1122 1493 1178">Private facility</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1235 1178 1278 1234">5</td> <td data-bbox="1278 1178 1493 1234">CHAM facility</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1235 1234 1278 1335">6</td> <td data-bbox="1278 1234 1493 1335">Home or household</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1235 1335 1278 1391">7</td> <td data-bbox="1278 1335 1493 1391">Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Hospital (gov)	2	Health centre (gov)	3	Pharmacy (gov)	4	Private facility	5	CHAM facility	6	Home or household	7	Other
1	Hospital (gov)															
2	Health centre (gov)															
3	Pharmacy (gov)															
4	Private facility															
5	CHAM facility															
6	Home or household															
7	Other															
job	What is your job there?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="1235 1453 1278 1516">1</td> <td data-bbox="1278 1453 1493 1516">Professional</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1235 1516 1278 1572">2</td> <td data-bbox="1278 1516 1493 1572">Farmer</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1235 1572 1278 1628">3</td> <td data-bbox="1278 1572 1493 1628">Labourer</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1235 1628 1278 1684">4</td> <td data-bbox="1278 1628 1493 1684">Housewife</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1235 1684 1278 1740">5</td> <td data-bbox="1278 1684 1493 1740">Other</td> </tr> </table>	1	Professional	2	Farmer	3	Labourer	4	Housewife	5	Other				
1	Professional															
2	Farmer															
3	Labourer															
4	Housewife															
5	Other															
g7	Hidden from user															
hivstatusi	24. What is the participant's HIV status?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="1235 1861 1278 1924">1</td> <td data-bbox="1278 1861 1493 1924">Positive</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1235 1924 1278 1980">0</td> <td data-bbox="1278 1924 1493 1980">Negative</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1235 1980 1278 2036">2</td> <td data-bbox="1278 1980 1493 2036">Exposed</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1235 2036 1278 2092">3</td> <td data-bbox="1278 2036 1493 2092">Prefer not to say</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1235 2092 1278 2141"></td> <td data-bbox="1278 2092 1493 2141"></td> </tr> </table>	1	Positive	0	Negative	2	Exposed	3	Prefer not to say						
1	Positive															
0	Negative															
2	Exposed															
3	Prefer not to say															

		99 Unknown								
hivstatus	25. What is the participant's HIV status?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Positive</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>Negative</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Prefer not to say</td> </tr> <tr> <td>99</td> <td>Unknown</td> </tr> </table>	1	Positive	0	Negative	3	Prefer not to say	99	Unknown
1	Positive									
0	Negative									
3	Prefer not to say									
99	Unknown									
hivstatusconf	26. Has this been confirmed in health passport?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
g8	Hidden from user									
hivsatusdate	27. Most recent HIV Test date	User selected date								
_hivsatusdate_dtype	27b. Is the date complete?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Complete (Day-Month-Year)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Partially complete (Month-Year)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Partially complete (Year Only)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>88</td> <td>Unknown</td> </tr> </table>	1	Complete (Day-Month-Year)	2	Partially complete (Month-Year)	3	Partially complete (Year Only)	88	Unknown
1	Complete (Day-Month-Year)									
2	Partially complete (Month-Year)									
3	Partially complete (Year Only)									
88	Unknown									
generated_note_name_101	You indicated that date is partially complete (Month-Year) but you have not entered 15 for day. Please go back and check the hint under the question.	User entered text								
generated_note_name_102	You indicated that date is partially complete (Year Only) but you have not entered 15 for day and Jun for month. Please go back and check the hint under the question.	User entered text								
hivtdur	Hidden from user									
hivtdurm	Hidden from user									
generated_note_name_105	Date of hiv test cannot be before you were born. Please navigate back and make necessary corrections.	User entered text								
prophyantibio	Receiving prophylactic antibiotics due to HIV infection?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
longtermhprob	Do you have any onging or long-term health problems?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
grpLongTermDisease	Hidden from user									

generated_note_name_109	Choose the long-term health problems participant has	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_110		1	Yes
		0	No
liverdisease	Chronic liver disease	1	Yes
		0	No
diabetis	Diabetes	1	Yes
		0	No
asthma	COPD/Asthma	1	Yes
		0	No
malignancy	Malignancy (solid organ)	1	Yes
		0	No
haemalignancy	Haematological malignancy	1	Yes
		0	No
kidneydisease	Chronic kidney disease	1	Yes
		0	No
cerebrodis	Cerebrovascular disease	1	Yes
		0	No
hypertension	Hypertension	1	Yes
		0	No
anaemia	Anaemia	1	Yes
		0	No
menthealthprob	Mental health problem	1	Yes
		0	No

rheumatic	Rheumatic heart disease	1	Yes
		0	No
ischaemic	Ischaemic heart disease	1	Yes
		0	No
gastritis	Gastritis/gastric ulcer/GORD	1	Yes
		0	No
gallstones	Gallstones	1	Yes
		0	No
othbiliarydis	Other biliary disease	1	Yes
		0	No
arthritis	Arthritis	1	Yes
		0	No
congenitalmal	Congenital malformations (state)	1	Yes
		0	No
othdis	Other (specify)	1	Yes
		0	No
unkdis	Unknown	1	Yes
		0	No
otherdiss	Please specify other long term medical condition	User entered text	
medregular	On any medications on a regular basis?	1	Yes
		0	No
meds	Hidden from user		
med_n	35.What medication are you on?	User entered text	
admitin6mth	Admitted to hospital for at least one night in the past six months?	1	Yes
		0	No

hospname	What hospital are they in?	User entered text						
admtwhen	When was the last time?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Within last 2 weeks</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>2 weeks to 1 month</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>1 to 6 months</td> </tr> </table>	1	Within last 2 weeks	2	2 weeks to 1 month	3	1 to 6 months
1	Within last 2 weeks							
2	2 weeks to 1 month							
3	1 to 6 months							
hsoppatientdays	How long have they been there for?	User entered integer						
hospguardian	Has the participant been a guardian in hospital over the last 6 months?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
hospnamegu	What hospital are they in?	User entered text						
admtwheng	When was the last time?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Within last 2 weeks</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>2 weeks to 1 month</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>1 to 6 months</td> </tr> </table>	1	Within last 2 weeks	2	2 weeks to 1 month	3	1 to 6 months
1	Within last 2 weeks							
2	2 weeks to 1 month							
3	1 to 6 months							
hsopguardiandays	How long have they been there for?	User entered integer						
fv	Hidden from user							
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_144		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
fvr	Any fever at the moment?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
fvrlast3mth	Any fever in last 3 months?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
diarrhoe	Any diarrhoea at the moment?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
diarrhoelast3moth	Any diarrhoea in last 3 months?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							

contctanimal	Have you had contact with animals who developed any symptoms of gastrointestinal disease over the last 12 months?	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>Unknown</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	2	Unknown
1	Yes							
0	No							
2	Unknown							
grpSpeciescc	Hidden from user							
sppdai0	Which species did you have contact with?	User entered text						
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_152		<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
contgaan1	Cow	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
contgaan2	Pig	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
contgaan3	Sheep	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
contgaan4	Goat	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
contgaan5	Dog	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
contgaan6	Cat	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
contgaan7	Horse	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
contgaan8	Donkey	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
contgaan9	Chicken	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td></td><td></td></tr> </table>	1	Yes				
1	Yes							

		0	No
contgaan99	Other Species	1	Yes
		0	No
contgaan99o	Please specify other species	User entered text	
an1	Hidden from user		
an1symp	Hidden from user		
generated_table_list_label_165	Which symptoms did the cows have?	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_166		1	Yes
		0	No
an1symptom1	Vomiting	1	Yes
		0	No
an1symptom2	Diarrhoea	1	Yes
		0	No
an1symptom3	Inappetance	1	Yes
		0	No
an1symptom99	Other	1	Yes
		0	No
an1symptoms1	Please specify other symptom	User entered text	
an1antibiosed	Were antibiotics used to treat the disease in the cows?	1	Yes
		0	No
		2	Unknown
an1grpAntibiotiUsed	Hidden from user		
generated_note_name_174	Which antibiotics were used?	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_175		1	Yes
		0	No
an1tetracyline	Tetracycline	1	Yes

		0	No
an1streptomycin	Streptomycin	1	Yes
		0	No
an1ampicilin	Ampicillin	1	Yes
		0	No
an1amoxicilinclav	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	1	Yes
		0	No
an1trimethoprim	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	1	Yes
		0	No
an1sulphonamide	Sulphonamide	1	Yes
		0	No
an1amoxicilin	Amoxicillin	1	Yes
		0	No
an1anti_unkon	Unknown	1	Yes
		0	No
an1oth	Other	1	Yes
		0	No
an1otht	Please specify other antibiotic	User entered text	
an1picpacket	Picture of packet	User captured image	
an1descrpacket	Description of packet	User entered text	
an2	Hidden from user		
an2symp	Hidden from user		
generated_table_list_label_190	Which symptoms did the pigs have?	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_191		1	Yes
		0	No

an2symptom1	Vomiting	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an2symptom2	Diarrhoea	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an2symptom3	Inappetance	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an2symptom99	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an2symptoms1	Please specify other symptom	User entered text						
an2antibiosed	Were antibiotics used to treat the disease in the pigs?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Unknown</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	2	Unknown
1	Yes							
0	No							
2	Unknown							
an2grpAntibiotiUsed	Hidden from user							
generated_note_name_199	Which antibiotics were used?	User entered text						
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_200		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an2tetracyline	Tetracycline	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an2streptomycin	Streptomycin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an2ampicilin	Ampicillin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an2amoxicilinclav	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							

an2trimethoprim	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an2sulphonamide	Sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an2amoxicilin	Amoxicillin	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an2anti_unkon	Unknown	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an2oth	Other	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an2otht	Please specify other antibiotic	User entered text				
an2picpacket	Picture of packet	User captured image				
an2descpacket	Description of packet	User entered text				
an3	Hidden from user					
an3symp	Hidden from user					
generated_table_list_label_215	Which symptoms did the sheep have?	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_216		<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an3symptom1	Vomiting	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an3symptom2	Diarrhoea	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an3symptom3	Inappetance	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an3symptom99	Other	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					

an3symptoms1	Please specify other symptom	User entered text						
an3antibiosed	Were antibiotics used to treat the disease in the sheep?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Unknown</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	2	Unknown
1	Yes							
0	No							
2	Unknown							
an3grpAntibiotiUsed	Hidden from user							
generated_note_name_224	Which antibiotics were used?	User entered text						
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_225		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an3tetracycline	Tetracycline	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an3streptomycin	Streptomycin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an3ampicilin	Ampicillin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an3amoxicilinclav	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an3trimethoprim	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an3sulphonamide	Sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an3amoxicilin	Amoxicillin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an3anti_unkon	Unknown	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							

an3oth	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an3otht	Please specify other antibiotic	User entered text						
an3picpacket	Picture of packet	User captured image						
an3descrpacket	Description of packet	User entered text						
an4	Hidden from user							
an4symp	Hidden from user							
generated_table_list_label_240	Which symptoms did the goats have?	User entered text						
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_241		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an4symptom1	Vomiting	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an4symptom2	Diarrhoea	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an4symptom3	Inappetance	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an4symptom99	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an4symptoms1	Please specify other symptom	User entered text						
an4antiboused	Were antibiotics used to treat the disease in the goats?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Unknown</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	2	Unknown
1	Yes							
0	No							
2	Unknown							
an4grpAntibiotiUsed	Hidden from user							
generated_note_name_249	Which antibiotics were used?	User entered text						
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_250		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							

an4tetracycline	Tetracycline	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an4streptomycin	Streptomycin	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an4ampicilin	Ampicillin	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an4amoxicilinclav	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an4trimethoprim	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an4sulphonamide	Sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an4amoxicilin	Amoxicillin	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an4anti_unkon	Unknown	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an4oth	Other	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an4otht	Please specify other antibiotic	User entered text				
an4picpacket	Picture of packet	User captured image				
an4descrpacket	Description of packet	User entered text				
an5	Hidden from user					
an5symp	Hidden from user					
generated_table_list_label_265	Which symptoms did the dogs have?	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_266		<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					

an5symptom1	Vomiting	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an5symptom2	Diarrhoea	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an5symptom3	Inappetance	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an5symptom99	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an5symptoms1	Please specify other symptom	User entered text						
an5antibiosed	Were antibiotics used to treat the disease in the dogs?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Unknown</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	2	Unknown
1	Yes							
0	No							
2	Unknown							
an5grpAntibiotiUsed	Hidden from user							
generated_note_name_274	Which antibiotics were used?	User entered text						
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_275		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an5tetracyline	Tetracycline	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an5streptomycin	Streptomycin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an5ampicilin	Ampicillin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an5amoxicilinclav	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							

an5trimethoprim	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an5sulphonamide	Sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an5amoxicilin	Amoxicillin	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an5anti_unkon	Unknown	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an5oth	Other	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an5otht	Please specify other antibiotic	User entered text				
an5picpacket	Picture of packet	User captured image				
an5descrpacket	Description of packet	User entered text				
an6	Hidden from user					
an6symp	Hidden from user					
generated_table_list_label_290	Which symptoms did the cats have?	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_291		<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an6symptom1	Vomiting	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an6symptom2	Diarrhoea	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an6symptom3	Inappetance	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an6symptom99	Other	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes		
1	Yes					

		0	No
an6symptoms1	Please specify other symptom	User entered text	
an6antiboused	Were antibiotics used to treat the disease in the cats?	1	Yes
		0	No
		2	Unknown
an6grpAntibiotiUsed	Hidden from user		
generated_note_name_299	Which antibiotics were used?	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_300		1	Yes
		0	No
an6tetracyline	Tetracycline	1	Yes
		0	No
an6streptomycin	Streptomycin	1	Yes
		0	No
an6ampicilin	Ampicillin	1	Yes
		0	No
an6amoxicilinclav	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	1	Yes
		0	No
an6trimethoprim	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	1	Yes
		0	No
an6sulphonamide	Sulphonamide	1	Yes
		0	No
an6amoxicilin	Amoxicillin	1	Yes
		0	No
an6anti_unkon	Unknown	1	Yes
		0	No

an6oth	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an6oht	Please specify other antibiotic	User entered text						
an6picpacket	Picture of packet	User captured image						
an6descrpacket	Description of packet	User entered text						
an7	Hidden from user							
an7symp	Hidden from user							
generated_table_list_label_315	Which symptoms did the horse have?	User entered text						
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_316		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an7symptom1	Vomiting	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an7symptom2	Diarrhoea	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an7symptom3	Inappetance	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an7symptom99	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an7symptoms1	Please specify other symptom	User entered text						
an7antibioused	Were antibiotics used to treat the disease in the horse?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Unknown</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	2	Unknown
1	Yes							
0	No							
2	Unknown							
an7grpAntibiotiUsed	Hidden from user							
generated_note_name_324	Which antibiotics were used?	User entered text						
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_325		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							

an7tetracyline	Tetracycline	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an7streptomycin	Streptomycin	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an7ampicilin	Ampicillin	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an7amoxicilinclav	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an7trimethoprim	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an7sulphonamide	Sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an7amoxicilin	Amoxicillin	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an7anti_unkon	Unknown	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an7oth	Other	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an7otht	Please specify other antibiotic	User entered text				
an7picpacket	Picture of packet	User captured image				
an7descrpacket	Description of packet	User entered text				
an8	Hidden from user					
an8symp	Hidden from user					
generated_table_list_label_340	Which symptoms did the donkeys have?	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_341		<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes		
1	Yes					

		0	No
an8symptom1	Vomiting	1	Yes
		0	No
an8symptom2	Diarrhoea	1	Yes
		0	No
an8symptom3	Inappetance	1	Yes
		0	No
an8symptom99	Other	1	Yes
		0	No
an8symptoms1	Please specify other symptom	User entered text	
an8antibiosed	Were antibiotics used to treat the disease in the donkeys?	1	Yes
		0	No
		2	Unknown
an8grpAntibiotiUsed	Hidden from user		
generated_note_name_349	Which antibiotics were used?	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_350		1	Yes
		0	No
an8tetracycline	Tetracycline	1	Yes
		0	No
an8streptomycin	Streptomycin	1	Yes
		0	No
an8ampicilin	Ampicillin	1	Yes
		0	No
an8amoxicilinclav	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	1	Yes
		0	No

an8trimethoprim	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an8sulphonamide	Sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an8amoxicilin	Amoxicillin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an8anti_unkon	Unknown	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an8oth	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an8otht	Please specify other antibiotic	User entered text				
an8picpacket	Picture of packet	User captured image				
an8descrpacket	Description of packet	User entered text				
an9	Hidden from user					
an9symp	Hidden from user					
generated_table_list_label_365	Which symptoms did the chickens have?	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_366		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an9symptom1	Vomiting	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an9symptom2	Diarrhoea	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
an9symptom3	Inappetance	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					

an9symptom99	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an9symptoms1	Please specify other symptom	User entered text						
an9antibiosed	Were antibiotics used to treat the disease in the chickens?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Unknown</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	2	Unknown
1	Yes							
0	No							
2	Unknown							
an9grpAntibiotiUsed	Hidden from user							
generated_note_name_374	Which antibiotics were used?	User entered text						
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_375		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an9tetracyline	Tetracycline	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an9streptomycin	Streptomycin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an9ampicilin	Ampicillin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an9amoxicilinclav	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an9trimethoprim	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an9sulphonamide	Sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an9amoxicilin	Amoxicillin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
an9anti_unkon	Unknown	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes				
1	Yes							

		0	No
an9oth	Other	1	Yes
		0	No
an9otht	Please specify other antibiotic	User entered text	
an9picpacket	Picture of packet	User captured image	
an9descpacket	Description of packet	User entered text	
an99	Hidden from user		
an99symp	Hidden from user		
generated_table_list_label_390	Which symptoms did the \${3} have?	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_391		1	Yes
		0	No
an99symptom1	Vomiting	1	Yes
		0	No
an99symptom2	Diarrhoea	1	Yes
		0	No
an99symptom3	Inappetance	1	Yes
		0	No
an99symptom99	Other	1	Yes
		0	No
an99symptoms1	Please specify other symptom	User entered text	
an99antiboused	Were antibiotics used to treat the disease in the \${3}?	1	Yes
		0	No
		2	Unknown
an99grpAntibiotiUsed	Hidden from user		
generated_note_name_399	Which antibiotics were used?	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_400		1	Yes

		0	No
an99tetracycline	Tetracycline	1	Yes
		0	No
an99streptomycin	Streptomycin	1	Yes
		0	No
an99ampicilin	Ampicillin	1	Yes
		0	No
an99amoxicilinclav	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	1	Yes
		0	No
an99trimethoprim	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	1	Yes
		0	No
an99sulphonamide	Sulphonamide	1	Yes
		0	No
an99amoxicilin	Amoxicillin	1	Yes
		0	No
an99anti_unkon	Unknown	1	Yes
		0	No
an99oth	Other	1	Yes
		0	No
an99otht	Please specify other antibiotic	User entered text	
an99picpacket	Picture of packet	User captured image	
an99descrpacket	Description of packet	User entered text	
hh1	Have you had contact with people who developed any symptoms of gastrointestinal disease over the last 12 months?	1	Yes
		0	No
		2	Unknown

hh1g	Hidden from user							
hh1symp	Hidden from user							
generated_table_list_label_416	Which symptoms did they have?	User entered text						
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_417		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
hh1symptom1	Vomiting	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
hh1symptom2	Diarrhoea	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
hh1symptom3	Inappetance	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
hh1symptom99	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
hh1symptoms1	Please specify other symptom	User entered text						
hh1antibiosed	Were antibiotics used to treat the disease?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Unknown</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No	2	Unknown
1	Yes							
0	No							
2	Unknown							
hh1grpAntibiotiUsed	Hidden from user							
generated_note_name_425	Which antibiotics were used?	User entered text						
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_426		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
hh1tetracyline	Tetracycline	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
hh1streptomycin	Streptomycin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							

hh1ampicilin	Ampicillin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
hh1amoxicilinclav	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
hh1trimethoprim	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
hh1sulphonamide	Sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
hh1amoxicilin	Amoxicillin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
hh1anti_unkon	Unknown	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
hh1oth	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
hh1otht	Please specify other antibiotic	User entered text				
hh1picpacket	Picture of packet	User captured image				
hh1descrpacket	Description of packet	User entered text				
antibio_receiv	Are you receiving antibiotics at the moment?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
grpAntibiotiReceived	Hidden from user					
generated_note_name_442	Which antibiotics are being used?	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_443		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
tetracyline_cur	Tetracycline	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					

streptomycin_cur	Streptomycin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
ampicilin_cur	Ampicillin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
amoxicilinclav_cur	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
trimethoprim_cur	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
sulphonamide_cur	Sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
amoxicilin_cur	Amoxicillin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
anti_unkon_cur	Unknown	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
oth_cur	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
oth_curt	Please specify other antibiotic	User entered text						
antibiophoto	Which antibiotics, please provide a photo of packet	User captured image						
descrpaket1	Description of packet	User entered text						
hp_confirm	Is this confirmed in the health passport or with packet?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No		
1	Yes							
0	No							
antibiowhere	Where did you get the antibiotics from?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>QECH</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Other hospital (gov)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Other clinic (gov)</td> </tr> </table>	1	QECH	2	Other hospital (gov)	3	Other clinic (gov)
1	QECH							
2	Other hospital (gov)							
3	Other clinic (gov)							

		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Otherpharmacy (gov)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Shop/market</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Traditional medical practitioner</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>Friend/family</td> </tr> <tr> <td>8</td> <td>Other (specify)</td> </tr> </table>	4	Otherpharmacy (gov)	5	Shop/market	6	Traditional medical practitioner	7	Friend/family	8	Other (specify)
4	Otherpharmacy (gov)											
5	Shop/market											
6	Traditional medical practitioner											
7	Friend/family											
8	Other (specify)											
antbiowhereo	Please specify where you get the antibiotics from	User entered text										
lastantbiowhen	When was the last course of antibiotics?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Within last 2 weeks</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>2 weeks to 1 month</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>1 to 6 months</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>6 months to 1 year</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>More than 1 year</td> </tr> </table>	1	Within last 2 weeks	2	2 weeks to 1 month	3	1 to 6 months	4	6 months to 1 year	5	More than 1 year
1	Within last 2 weeks											
2	2 weeks to 1 month											
3	1 to 6 months											
4	6 months to 1 year											
5	More than 1 year											
grpLastAntibiotics	Hidden from user											
generated_note_name_461	Which ones?	User entered text										
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_462		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
tetracyline_last	Tetracycline	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
streptomycin_last	Streptomycin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
ampicilin_last	Ampicillin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
amoxicilinclav_last	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
trimethoprim_last	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											

sulphonamide_last	Sulphonamide	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No								
1	Yes													
0	No													
amoxicilin_last	Amoxicillin	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No								
1	Yes													
0	No													
anti_unkon_last	Unknown	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No								
1	Yes													
0	No													
oth_last	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No								
1	Yes													
0	No													
oth_lastt	Please specify other antibiotic	User entered text												
travelfreqc	How frequently do you travel outside of Chikwawa?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Never</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Most days</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>At least once a week</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>A few times a month</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>A few times a year</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Live outside Chikwawa</td> </tr> </table>	1	Never	2	Most days	3	At least once a week	4	A few times a month	5	A few times a year	6	Live outside Chikwawa
1	Never													
2	Most days													
3	At least once a week													
4	A few times a month													
5	A few times a year													
6	Live outside Chikwawa													
travelfreqb	How frequently do you travel outside of BT?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Never</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Most days</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>At least once a week</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>A few times a month</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>A few times a year</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>Live outside BT</td> </tr> </table>	1	Never	2	Most days	3	At least once a week	4	A few times a month	5	A few times a year	6	Live outside BT
1	Never													
2	Most days													
3	At least once a week													
4	A few times a month													
5	A few times a year													
6	Live outside BT													
travelpurp	What is the usual purpose of this travel?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Visiting friends or family</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Work</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Healthcare</td> </tr> </table>	1	Visiting friends or family	2	Work	3	Healthcare						
1	Visiting friends or family													
2	Work													
3	Healthcare													

		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table>	4	Other	5	Don't know						
4	Other											
5	Don't know											
traveloutmw	Have you travelled outside Malawi in the last year?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
taveloutmwwhy	What was the purpose of your travel outside Malawi?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Visiting friends or family</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>Work</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>Healthcare</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>Other</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>Don't know</td> </tr> </table>	1	Visiting friends or family	2	Work	3	Healthcare	4	Other	5	Don't know
1	Visiting friends or family											
2	Work											
3	Healthcare											
4	Other											
5	Don't know											
tr	Hidden from user											
traveloutmwcountry	Which country did you travel to?	User entered text										
traveloutmwcity	Which city did you travel to?	User entered text										
traveloutmwwhen	When did you travel	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Within last 2 weeks</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>2 weeks to 1 month</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>1 to 6 months</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>6 months to 1 year</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>More than 1 year</td> </tr> </table>	1	Within last 2 weeks	2	2 weeks to 1 month	3	1 to 6 months	4	6 months to 1 year	5	More than 1 year
1	Within last 2 weeks											
2	2 weeks to 1 month											
3	1 to 6 months											
4	6 months to 1 year											
5	More than 1 year											
hcooutmw	Did you receive healthcare whilst there?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
antibioutmw	Any antibiotics whilst there?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
grpAntibioticsOutofMW	Hidden from user											
generated_note_name_486	Do you remember what these were?	User entered text										
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_487		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No						
1	Yes											
0	No											
tetracyline_outmw	Tetracycline	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes								
1	Yes											

		0	No
streptomycin_outmw	Streptomycin	1	Yes
		0	No
ampicilin_outmw	Ampicillin	1	Yes
		0	No
amoxicilinclav_outmw	Amoxicillin-clavulanate	1	Yes
		0	No
trimethoprim_outmw	Trimethoprim sulphonamide	1	Yes
		0	No
sulphonamide_outmw	Sulphonamide	1	Yes
		0	No
amoxicilin_outmw	Amoxicillin	1	Yes
		0	No
anti_unkon_outmw	Unknown	1	Yes
		0	No
oth_outmw	Other	1	Yes
		0	No
oth_outmwt	Please specify other antibiotic	User entered text	
grpSpecies	Hidden from user		
sppdai0	Which species are you in contact with daily in Blantyre?	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_500		1	Yes
		0	No
sppdai0cow	Cow	1	Yes
		0	No

sppdai0pig	Pig	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
sppdai0she	Sheep	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
sppdai0goa	Goat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
sppdai0dog	Dog	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
sppdai0cat	Cat	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
sppdai0hor	Horse	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
sppdai0don	Donkey	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
sppdai0bir	Chicken	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
sppdai0other	Other Species	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
sppdai0othsp	Other (specify species)	User entered text				
othersp1	Do you want to add another species?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
sppdai0othsp1	Other (specify species)	User entered text				
othersp2	Do you want to add another species?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					

sppdai0othsp2	Other (specify species)	User entered text				
dis	Hidden from user					
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_517		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
dispoaniurine	Do you dispose of animal urine or urine soiled material?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
dispoanifaecal	Do you dispose of animal faecal material?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
washhands	Do you wash your hands during the day?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
wh	Hidden from user					
generated_table_list_label_521	when do you wash them?	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_522		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
whw1	After urinating	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
whw1a	After defecating	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
whw2	Before cooking	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
whw3	Whilst washing	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
whw4	After handling animals	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					

whw9	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No										
1	Yes															
0	No															
whw9t	Please specify other	User entered text														
usp	Hidden from user															
generated_table_list_label_530	Do you use soap	User entered text														
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_531		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No										
1	Yes															
0	No															
usesoap1	Before preparing food	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No										
1	Yes															
0	No															
usesoap2	After urinating	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No										
1	Yes															
0	No															
usesoap3	After defecating	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No										
1	Yes															
0	No															
usesoap4	After handling animals	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No										
1	Yes															
0	No															
usesoap5	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No										
1	Yes															
0	No															
usesoap5o	Please specify other	User entered text														
rodents	How many rodents have you seen within a 5 metre radius of your house over the last week	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>3</td> <td>3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>4</td> <td>4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>5</td> <td>5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>6</td> <td>More</td> </tr> <tr> <td>7</td> <td>None</td> </tr> </table>	1	1	2	2	3	3	4	4	5	5	6	More	7	None
1	1															
2	2															
3	3															
4	4															
5	5															
6	More															
7	None															
rodentsinside	How many rodents have you seen inside your house within the last week?	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	1	1												
1	1															

		<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr><td>2</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>3</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>4</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>5</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>More</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>None</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	2	2	3	3	4	4	5	5	6	More	7	None		
2	2															
3	3															
4	4															
5	5															
6	More															
7	None															
rodentobservfreq	How often do you observe new rodent excreta within the compound perimeter?	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr><td>1</td><td>Once daily</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>More than once daily</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Once weekly</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Once monthly</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Less frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Never</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	1	Once daily	2	More than once daily	3	Once weekly	4	Once monthly	5	Less frequently	6	Never		
1	Once daily															
2	More than once daily															
3	Once weekly															
4	Once monthly															
5	Less frequently															
6	Never															
geckoseenfreq	How many times daily are geckos seen around the house?	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr><td>1</td><td>Once daily</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>More than once daily</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Once weekly</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Once monthly</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Less frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Never</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Constantly</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	1	Once daily	2	More than once daily	3	Once weekly	4	Once monthly	5	Less frequently	6	Never	7	Constantly
1	Once daily															
2	More than once daily															
3	Once weekly															
4	Once monthly															
5	Less frequently															
6	Never															
7	Constantly															
geckobservfreq	How often do you observe new gecko excreta within the compound perimeter?	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr><td>1</td><td>Once daily</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>More than once daily</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Once weekly</td></tr> <tr><td>4</td><td>Once monthly</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Less frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Never</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	1	Once daily	2	More than once daily	3	Once weekly	4	Once monthly	5	Less frequently	6	Never		
1	Once daily															
2	More than once daily															
3	Once weekly															
4	Once monthly															
5	Less frequently															
6	Never															
birdseenfreq	How many times daily are wild birds seen around the house?	<table border="1"> <tbody> <tr><td>1</td><td>Once daily</td></tr> <tr><td>2</td><td>More than once daily</td></tr> <tr><td>3</td><td>Once weekly</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	1	Once daily	2	More than once daily	3	Once weekly								
1	Once daily															
2	More than once daily															
3	Once weekly															

		<table border="1"> <tr><td>4</td><td>Once monthly</td></tr> <tr><td>5</td><td>Less frequently</td></tr> <tr><td>6</td><td>Never</td></tr> <tr><td>7</td><td>Constantly</td></tr> </table>	4	Once monthly	5	Less frequently	6	Never	7	Constantly
4	Once monthly									
5	Less frequently									
6	Never									
7	Constantly									
grpCowActivities	Hidden from user									
generated_note_name_545	What COW related activities do you undertake?	User entered text								
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_546		<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
grazingcow	Taking to grazing	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
feedcow	Feeding	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
kholamgtcow	Management around the Khola	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
medtreatcow	Medical treatment	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
cowother	Other	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
cowothersp	Specify other cow related activites	User entered text								
grpPigActivities	Hidden from user									
generated_note_name_554	What PIG related activities do you undertake?	User entered text								
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_555		<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
feedpig	Feeding	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> <tr><td>0</td><td>No</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No				
1	Yes									
0	No									
husbandpig	Husbandary in the home	<table border="1"> <tr><td>1</td><td>Yes</td></tr> </table>	1	Yes						
1	Yes									

		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	0	No		
0	No					
roampig	Taking to roaming area	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
slaughterpig	Taking to slaughter	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
othrpig	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
othrpigsp	Specify other pig related activities	User entered text				
grpSheepActivities	Hidden from user					
anact0she	What SHEEP related activities do you undertake?	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_564		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
grazingshe	Taking to grazing	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
feedshe	Feeding	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
kholamgtshe	Management around the Khola	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
medtreatshe	Medical treatment	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
sheother	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
sheothersp	Specify other sheep related activities	User entered text				
grpGoatActivities	Hidden from user					

anact0goa	What GOAT related activities do you undertake?	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_573		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
grazinggoa	Taking to grazing	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
feedgoa	Feeding	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
kholamgtgoa	Management around the Khola	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
medtreatgoa	Medical treatment	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
goaothor	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
goaothersp	Specify other goat related activities	User entered text				
grpDog	Hidden from user					
generated_note_name_581	What DOG related activities do you undertake?	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_582		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
dogfeed	Feeding	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
dogcleaningmess	Cleaning up mess	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
dogwalking	Walking	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
doggivemed	Giving mediations					

		1	Yes
		0	No
dogoth	Other	1	Yes
		0	No
dogothsp	Specify other dog related activities	User entered text	
grpCat	Hidden from user		
generated_note_name_590	What CAT related activities do you undertake?	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_591		1	Yes
		0	No
catfeed	Feeding	1	Yes
		0	No
catcleaningmess	Cleaning up mess	1	Yes
		0	No
catgivemed	Giving medications	1	Yes
		0	No
catoth	Other	1	Yes
		0	No
catothsp	Specify other cat related activities	User entered text	
grpHorseActivities	Hidden from user		
anact0hor	What HORSE related activities do you undertake?	User entered text	
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_599		1	Yes
		0	No
grazinghor	Taking to grazing	1	Yes
		0	No
feedhor	Feeding	1	Yes
		0	No

kholamgthor	Management around the Khola	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
medtreathor	Medical treatment	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
horother	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
horothersp	Specify other horse related activities	User entered text				
grpDonkeyActivities	Hidden from user					
anact0Don	What DONKEY related activities do you undertake?	User entered text				
reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_608		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
grazingdon	Taking to grazing	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
feeddon	Feeding	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
kholamgtdon	Management around the Khola	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
medtreatdon	Medical treatment	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
donother	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
donothersp	Specify other donkey related activities	User entered text				
grpChickenActivities	Hidden from user					
generated_note_name_616	What CHICKEN related activities do you undertake?	User entered text				

reserved_name_for_field_list_labels_617		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
cleaningchi	Cleaning coop	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
feedchi	Feeding	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
givemedchi	Giving medication	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
letoutchi	Letting out and catching	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
chioth	Other	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>1</td> <td>Yes</td> </tr> <tr> <td>0</td> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	1	Yes	0	No
1	Yes					
0	No					
chiothsp	Specify other chicken related activities	User entered text				
othersp1t	Specify \${4} related activities	User entered text				
othersp2t	Specify \${5} related activities	User entered text				
othersp3t	Specify \${6} related activities	User entered text				
grplnit	Hidden from user					
note_end	You have completed data collection for this participant. On the next screen please remember to: 1. Verify that 'Mark form as finalized' is ticked 2. Click 'Save Form and Exit'	User entered text				
init_staff	Staff initials	User entered text				
calc_sinit	Hidden from user					
generated_note_name_633	The provided staff initials: \${7} are not valid. Please navigate back and provide valid staff initials.	User entered text				
meta	Hidden from user					
instanceID	Hidden from user					
instanceName	Hidden from user					